

ENDODONTIC MANAGEMENT OF TWO ROOTED MANDIBULAR SECOND PREMOLAR: (A CASE REPORT)

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Abstract :-Understanding the root and canal anatomy is pivotal before initiating endodontic surgical procedures. Any missed canal will cause treatment failure and ultimately lead to tooth extraction in this era of tooth conservation. Mandibular second premolars have attracted researchers and clinicians for having aberrant anatomy.

Variations in the number of roots or canals may not be discerned on 2D radiographs and may become apparent during treatment procedures. The occurrence of two roots in the lower second premolar has been reported in the current case. Here, in this case, the authors have described the clinical course of the patient along with the management of these two rooted mandibular second premolars.

Keywords:- Two rooted premolar, Unusal anatomy, negotiation, missed canal.

Introduction :- Residual debris after obturating the root canals serves as a nidus for re-infection and subsequent failure of the root canal therapy (RCT). The primary purpose of the endodontic procedures is to eliminate the necrotic debris and microorganisms present in the canals and obturate it with a biologically inert material to achieve a complete three-dimensional seal¹.

The number of canals in a tooth varies based on the number of roots, root dimensions, tooth location, etc. The typical anatomies of all the roots and their canals have been documented in the literature. However, a departure from this typical form may lead to endodontic mishaps. Due to this reason, a thorough knowledge of root morphology is a prime requisite before initiating RCT².

The mandibular second premolars have been extensively studied in the literature because of wide-spectrum variations in the root and its canal anatomy. The extra root will possess one or more canals that dental surgeons may neglect. In their systematic review, Wolf et al. reported less than 1.5% occurrence of two rooted mandibular second premolar³.

The author did an extensive literature review for variations in root numbers about lower second premolars. However, data or a report regarding multiple roots in this tooth was not sufficient. This shows that the dental clinicians might not have frequently encountered additional roots in the lower second premolar.

The current study attempts to alert the dental fraternity about such variations in root and canal numbers. It is essential to be aware of such deviations from the normal before initiating RCT.

CASE REPORT :-

A 27-year-old male reported to the department of Conservative dentistry and endodontics with a chief complaint of food lodgment in the lower left back region of the jaw for 10-12 days. Patient was apparently alright before 6 months, then he experienced pain in lower left back region of a jaw.

Pain was aggravated on heat & subsided on taking medication. Pain was spontaneous in nature. Medical history of the patient was non contributory. History of amalgam restoration with 37 a year ago. On clinical examination, the tooth (35) was deeply carious and tender to vertical percussion. There was a presence of prolonged sensitivity to hot and cold. Electric pulp testing & cold testing showed hypersensitive & lingering response with 35. Deep proximal caries with 35 (DISTAL APPROACH). On vertical percussion, tenderness was positive with 35.

The radiograph of the mandibular left second premolar(35) showed radiolucency approaching pulp. On radiographic examination, caries was present on the proximal surface of the tooth(**DISTALLY**), two unusual and unexpected findings of the presence of two roots with 35 and no periapical inflammation. Two roots were found and distinguished as **BUCCAL & LINGUAL ROOTS**.

FIGURE :- PREOPERATIVE RADIOGRAPH

CASE REPORT

Root canal treatment was planned for the patient, and informed consent was obtained before the initiation of treatment. Profound local anesthesia was achieved using lignocaine hydrochloride with adrenaline in the ratio (1:1,00,000).

Under proper rubber dam isolation (GDC Fine Crafted Dental Pvt. Ltd., India), complete distant proximal caries was removed, and an access opening was done to expose the pulp canal orifice using 245, 169-L bur. The patency of both the canals in both buccal and lingual roots was confirmed with the #10 K (MANI, Japan) file. Subsequently, the initial working length was determined using #15 K file (MANI, Japan) and Root Zx Mini Apex Locator (J. Morita USA, Inc.) with the help of radiographic images .

Biomechanical preparation was done using hand-operated files and nickel-titanium rotary instruments (Dentsply, Switzerland). Thorough irrigation with 5.25% NaOCl, normal saline, and 0.2% chlorhexidine was also done simultaneously. The master cone fit was checked and confirmed on the radiograph following the final working length determination.

Canals were dried using sterile paper points, and obturation was done with both the roots, followed by post-endodontic composite restoration. A postoperative radiograph was taken, and the complete hermetic seal was verified with a horizontally angulated post-treatment radiograph.

FIGURE :- ACCESS OPENING, WORKING LENGTH RADIOGRAPH, MASTERCONE RADIOGRAPH, POST -OBTURATION RADIOGRAPH

DISCUSSION

As the complex anatomy of the root and canal systems along with the changes in the internal anatomy of teeth, strategic planning, and aids to diagnose such variable anatomy using preoperative cone beam-computed tomography or

multiangle radiographs are very important⁴, incidences of an additional root and canals in mandibular premolars may provide a significant endodontic difficulty, thereby increasing the chances of endodontics failures^{5,6}.

According to research, these findings are clinically critical as the mandibular premolars possess a great failure rate⁷. Failure to detect the existence of additional roots or canals might result in accidents such as acute flare-ups during treatment and endodontic therapy failure. For complete removal of the infection foci and prevention of disease recurrence, negotiation of main canals in all the roots of a tooth is essential⁸.

Using various diagnostic aids such as dental microscope and computed tomography techniques may be an effective way to discover missed canals rather than routine radiographs that give a two-dimensional image of the root structure^{9,10}.

Lower premolars have gained considerable attention from the clinical world due to wide-spectrum occurrences of morphological aberrations in root and canal systems¹¹. Not much literature is available regarding the lower second premolar compared with first premolars. Encountering anatomical deviations in second premolars, therefore, may create clinical challenges and symptoms persist for a longer time.

Arayasantiparb et al. reported that multiple roots in the first premolar were approximately 5.73%, while surprisingly, the authors did not find any second premolar with additional roots in the Thai population¹². Dosunmu et al. reported that the prevalence of two rooted mandibular first and second premolars is 1.8%-2.1% and 0.4%, respectively¹³. In this report, it was found that the mandibular second premolar is double rooted.

The current case represents an unusual finding of an additional root with #35 in an adolescent patient. Radiographic interpretation revealed no complex internal anatomy of the tooth structure that may require special attention. As the computed tomography facility was not available at the hospital, intraoperative periapical radiographs with different angles showed the presence of buccal and lingual roots with two distinct canals with #35.

The treatment course of the patient was normal, and all the canals were obturated to achieve a three-dimensional hermetic seal. Because of the clinician's awareness of the probabilities of unusual anatomy, radiographs from different angles were made to assess the root morphology. Further, the authors emphasize the necessity of 3D modeling of the tooth structure if the clinician is expecting any abnormal morphology through radiographic images. Also, training should be employed to assess the tooth 3D images and modeling.

CONCLUSION

The clinicians must be able to recognize the existence of unusual and unexpected variations in the root anatomy and canal configuration. To obtain a good clinical outcome and a complete understanding of root canal anatomy and its variations, careful radiographic interpretation associated with clinical inspection is important before initiating RCT. In the present case, exact root morphology and number cannot be apparent with just one 2D radiographic image. Hence, the use of multiple radiographs or computed radiography facility assists in detecting such variations. Conceivably, the clinical success in this case could be accredited to judicious planning, investigation, biomechanical preparation, and obturation of all the canals in both the roots of #35.

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